

USE SANDWICH COMPOSITES TO MAKE PASSENGER CAR COMPONENTS FOR RAIL TRAIN APPLICATION

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Abstract: Fast train is booming in China. To use sandwich composites construction in the train passenger car manufacturing is a right solution to reduce weight and energy consume, and then increase train speed further because they comprise the characters of the high ratios of stiffness and strength to weight, and the flexibility of designing and manufacturing. In our company's Rail Car Integral Module (CIM) division, the rigid structural foam materials, such as PET, PMI and other foams, are used as cores with glass fiber and resin for making sandwich composite components, including floor panel, division wall, bath room module, sleeping cabinet module, bar table, door, seat unit, side wall and front cap etc. The application research works started from product design and analysis, and then moved to mold design by computer software. The prototypes are made by using our self-made molds and different lamination methods, such as prepreg heat pressing, hand lay-up with vacuum bagging and vacuum infusion, for evaluating and mechanical tests. The prototyping components were installed in a display passenger car for comprehension evaluation. The test results show that the foam cored sandwich components possess the advantages of light weight, higher flexural stiffness and strength, corrosion resistance, thermal insulation and easy manufacturing etc. compared with the solid FRP and metal structures. The study also show that The laminating methods of prepreg heat pressing and hand lay-up with vacuum bagging are better than vacuum infusion for making the sandwich components because the flame retardant fillers will reduce the flow ability of resin and generate a non-uniform skin lamination.

Keywords: sandwich composites, foam cores, rail train, passenger car

1. Introduction

Due to fast progress of high speed train in China, the new materials for rail car manufacturing are introduced rapidly to the market. Structural foams are kinds of rigid core materials for sandwich composite application. For reducing the weight of the rail cars, and for reducing the power consuming and for protecting our environment, the foam cored sandwich composite components are being used to replace the traditional plywood and solid fiber glass composites because of their properties of low weight, high ratio of bending modulus to weight, heat insulation and high corrosive resistance. These types materials have been used for making the passenger cars of the rail train in Austria, Germany, Netherland and Australia etc [1], [2], [3].

This work started from product design and analysis, and then moved to mold design by computer software. The sandwich composite prototypes are made by using our self-made molds and different lamination methods, such as prepreg heat pressing, hand lay-up with vacuum bagging and vacuum infusion, for evaluating and mechanical tests. The prototyping components were installed in a display passenger car for comprehension evaluation.

2. Experiment

2.1 Materials and Processes

The components of the rail passenger car were made by the materials shown in the Table 1, and the processes shown in Figure 1. The solid fiber glass composite panels with thickness of 3 mm and 5 mm were laminated by vacuum infusion as the comparison with the sandwich side wall and the

sandwich division wall, respectively. A panel with construction of 0.5 mm aluminum skin and 7 mm aluminum honeycomb core was made as a ceiling wall for comparison; a panel with construction of 1 mm aluminum skin and 6 mm aluminum core was made as a side wall for comparison.

2.2 Testing

The impact test of Front Cap was conducted following UIC 651 -2002, (International Union of Railways), "Layout of driver's cabs in locomotives, railcars, multiple unit trains and driving trailers" [4].

The ceiling panels, side wall panels and division panels were tested following ASTM D790 method by using the support span of 200 mm, three points model, flat load head with the width of 20 mm. The sample dimensions were 350 mm x 60 mm, the test speed was 5 mm/min. The load readings were taken when the deflection was 3 mm and 5 mm respectively, the maximum load also was recorded. The curve of the load values vs. the deflection was plotted for comparing the strength of the different panel constructions.

Table 1. Lamination schedules of the components

Part Name	Resin	Top skin		Strucell® foam core type	Core Thickness (mm)	Bottom skin	
		Thickness after curing (mm)	Glass laminates			Thickness after curing (mm)	Glass laminates
Front cap	Ashland F645TFE-F207 Unsaturated Polyester	4	2 layers 300g/ m ² CSM, 3 layers 1200 g/m ² -45/90/45 Triaxil	P60	26	4	1layer 600 g/m ² 0/90 Biaxia, 2 layers 1200g/m ² -45/90/45 Triaxil, 2 layer 300g/m ² CSM
Celling panel	DSM P68V-994 Unsaturated Polyester	1	1 layer 1200g/m ² -45/90/45 Triaxial	P60	6.5	0.5	1 layer 800g/m ² -45/90/45 Triaxil
Side wall panel	DSM P68V-994 Unsaturated Polyester	1	1 layer 1200g/m ² -45/90/45 Triaxial	P60	6	1	1 layer 1200g/m ² -45/90/45 Triaxial
Division wall	Huake HS-501 Unsaturated Polyester	1	1 layer 300g/ m ² CSM, 1 layer 400 g/m ² 0/90 Biaxial	P60	8	1	1 layer 300g/ m ² CSM, 1 layer 400 g/m ² 0/90 Biaxial
Chair	Huake HS-501 Unsaturated Polyester	2	2 layer 300g/ m ² CSM, 2 layer 400 g/m ² 0/90 Biaxial	P80	5	2	2 layer 300g/ m ² CSM, 2 layer 400 g/m ² 0/90 Biaxial

Vacuum infusion process: laying the core and glass fabrics on the mold >> covering by vacuum film >> leading the resin to the mold >> curing >> trimming the edge >> product

Hand laying up and vacuum bagging: spraying resin, then laying down glass fabrics on the mold and spraying resin on the fabric >> laying down the core on the bottom skin >> spraying resin on the core, laying the fabrics on the core, then spraying the resin >> laying vacuum film on the laminate >> drawing vacuum >> curing >> trimming the edge >> product

Fig. 1. Vacuum infusion and hand lay-up vacuum bagging processes

3. Result and Discussion

3.1 Front Cap

The front cap of the passenger car of the rail train was shown in Figure 2. High speed impact test was conducted for evaluating the front cap according to UIC 651 [4]. The result shows the sandwich structure with Strucell® foam as core passed the impact test. The front cap after testing is shown in the Figure 3. The impact test results proved that the sandwich structure composites are safe for making the driver’s cab.

Fig. 2. Front cap with sandwich structure was made by vacuum infusion and Strucell® foam core.

Fig. 3. High speed impact test on the front cap

3.2 Ceiling panel

Flexural test results of ceiling panels are showed in Fig. 5 and Table 1. The set-up of the flexural test is shown in Figure 4. The flexural property of FRP sandwich structure composites is much stiffer and stronger than that of Al honeycomb sandwich structure composites.

Table 2. Flexural test results of ceiling panels

Flexural property	FRP skin + Structural foam core +	Al panel + Al honeycomb
	FRP skin 1 mm +6.5 mm +0.5 mm	core + Al panel 0.5 mm +7 mm +0.5 mm
Max force at yield (N)	766	330
Force at 3mm deformation (N)	405	257

Fig. 4. Flexural test set up

Fig.5. Flexural test results of ceiling panels

3.3 Side wall panel

Flexural test results of side wall panels are showed in **Figure 6** and **Table 2**. The photos of the ceiling

panel and the side wall panel were shown in the **Figure 7**. The results show that FRP sandwich structure composites have the best flexural property of the three kinds of panels.

Table 3. Flexural test results of side wall panels

Flexural property	FRP skin + structural foam core + FRP skin 1.0mm+6.0mm+1.0mm	3mm Solid FRP	Al panel + Al honeycomb core + Al panel 1.0mm+6.0mm+1.0mm
Max force at yield (N)	766	479	367
Force at 3mm deformation (N)	405	146	283

Fig. 6. Flexural test results of side wall panels

Fig. 7. Side wall panel and ceiling panel were made by using

3.4 Division wall and seat unit

The division wall and the seat unit made by the sandwich composites are shown in **Figure 8** and **Figure 9**. The flexural test results of division wall are shown in **Table 4**. It is obvious that FRP sandwich structure composites gave higher bending strength for making division wall. Flexural property of seat unit is similar to the results of the division wall.

Table 4. Flexural test results of division wall

Flexural property	FRP skin + structural foam core + FRP skin 1.0mm+8.0mm+1.0mm	5mm solid FRP
Max force at yield (N)	1030	858
Force at 3mm deformation (N)	607	146

Fig. 8. Division wall was made by using foam core and vacuum infusion process

Fig. 9. Seat unit was made by vacuum infusion

3.5 Processing method comparison

Two processing methods were used for making the composite parts in this work. The comparison of two methods is listed in Table 5. By using vacuum infusion process, the advantages are to provide good quality and minimize the environmental

pollution. The quality is very important for making the railway cab, and to protect our environment also is important. Therefore, the vacuum infusion is a major process used in this work and in our production process.

Table 5. The comparison of processing methods

Category	Vacuum Infusion	Hand lay-up vacuum bagging
Numbers of molds	20~25 (single mode)	20~25 (single mode)
Materials of molds	FRP	FRP
number of product per mold	200~500	200~500
Advantages	(a) Smooth surface both side (b) Less air bubble (c) Use less resin (d) Low environmental pollution (e) quality is reliable	(a) No size limit (b) Can use resin with high viscosity, and with filler and additives (c) low supply cost
Shortages	(a) Hard to make big size part (b) long preparing time (c) Not suitable for resin with filler (d) High supply cost	(a) Not easy to control air pollution (b) Use more resin (c) Not suitable for mass production

3.5 The advantages of sandwich structure composites with Strucell® foam as core

(a) The components made by the foam core sandwich composites have light weight, high flexural stiffness and strength, which meet the requirements of high-speed railway train for reducing the weight and the building cost.

(b) The composite components can be made into fire retardant grade by mixing the additives in the liquid resin. The parts made in this work have met the requirements of the Grade S4, SR2 and ST2 according to DIN 5510-2. They also in accordance with NF F16-101, with fire class M1 and F1.

(c) By using sandwich structure, the components are easy to be designed and made into different shapes, such as flat, single and double curved surface panel, and any 3D parts. They are suitable for mass production.

(d) The foam core sandwich composites also provide the corrosion resistance, weather resistance and thermal insulation.

(e) By designing and using right materials, the sandwich components can be made into the sound insulation that provide comfort environment in the passenger car of the fast train.

4 Conclusions

After analyzing all results of the work, it can be concluded that the sandwich structure composites with Strucell® foam as core and fiber glass/resin composite skin can be used for making the components of railway vehicles. Their favorable properties, such as light weight, flame resistance,

and sound insulation, are all better than Aluminum honeycomb composite and solid fiber glass composites.

Reference

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